

FEATURE OF PROVIDING SOCIAL AND LEGAL ASSISTANCE TO MINORS

Sultonov Bakhriddin Murodovich
Employee of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract: The article highlights the role of the system of social and legal assistance to minors in ensuring a peaceful and prosperous life for the population, combating crime and other offenses, maintaining public order, and implementing other vital tasks.

Key words: social and legal assistance to minors, behavior, preventive work, minors, training, responsibility, commission, medical and preventive institutions.

In recent years, our country has implemented large-scale reforms based on a clear approach in the sphere of internal affairs agencies, in particular, in the penal system.

A number of regulatory legal documents have been adopted aimed at further improving the functioning of this system, expanding the scope of rights and legitimate interests of persons serving sentences, and improving the conditions of their detention.

The internal affairs bodies have a special role in ensuring a peaceful and prosperous life for the population, combating crime and other offenses, maintaining public order, and performing other vital tasks. Over the years of independence, effective work has been carried out to transform the internal affairs bodies from a punitive and control body into a structure that protects the interests of the people, society, and the state.

As a result of the systemic measures taken over the past period, certain results have been achieved in preventing and suppressing crimes and other offenses, protecting public order and ensuring public safety, protecting the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021, No. 6196¹ "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies to a qualitatively new level in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime", an electronic system for preventive registration of persons was introduced from July 1, 2021. According to it, key tasks are defined to ensure the principle of a "Safe educational institution".

These laws provide the legal basis for such relations as care for minors, providing them with legal and social protection, supporting their initiatives and guaranteeing their free choice of ways to realize their interests. Today, our main guideline for the development of our youth as a comprehensively developed individual is Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Everyone has the right to education". Free general education is guaranteed by the state.

In addition to protecting the rights and freedoms of minors, important tasks in this area are identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that negatively affect them, organizing the prevention of neglect and delinquency among them, taking measures for social adaptation and social rehabilitation of minors who have committed offenses and need social

protection. The adoption of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No. 490 dated August 3, 2021² "On measures to further improve the provision of social and legal assistance to minors" is also evidence of large-scale implementation of work aimed at raising minors as full-fledged, full-fledged individuals and healthy children.

According to Article 49¹ of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 28, 2019 No. 558 ³"On amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan", violation of the requirements on the prohibition of the use of minors in work that may harm their health, safety or morality, shall entail a fine of ten to twenty minimum wages. The same offense committed repeatedly within a year after the imposition of an administrative penalty, shall entail a fine of twenty to thirty minimum wages. In accordance with Part One of Article 51 of this Law, committing an offense related to administrative coercion to work of a minor, shall entail a fine of thirty to fifty minimum wages. It is indicated that a similar offense committed repeatedly within a year after the imposition of an administrative penalty shall entail the imposition of a fine in the amount of fifty to one hundred minimum wages.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency" dated September 29, 2010 plays an important role in preventing juvenile delinquency, organizing and implementing preventive work among them, and defines its main directions. Article 3⁴ of the Law establishes the following basic concepts of preventing juvenile delinquency and crime:

prevention of juvenile delinquency and crime is a system of social, legal, medical and other measures implemented in conjunction with individual preventive work aimed at identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that contribute to delinquency, neglect of minors, their commission of offenses or other antisocial actions;

a minor in a socially dangerous situation is a minor who, due to the lack of supervision or care, creates a danger to his life or health or is in conditions that do not meet the requirements of his maintenance, upbringing and education, or who has committed a crime or other antisocial behavior;

a family in a socially dangerous situation is a family in which parents or persons replacing parents evade or improperly fulfill their responsibilities for the maintenance, upbringing and education of minors, negatively influence their behavior, and treat them cruelly;

a neglected child is a minor whose behavior has become uncontrollable due to evasion or improper fulfillment by parents or persons replacing them of their responsibilities for the maintenance, upbringing and education of the minor;

individual preventive work - activities aimed at the timely identification of minors and families in a socially dangerous situation, as well as their social and pedagogical rehabilitation and the prevention of minors committing offenses or other antisocial behavior;

antisocial behavior is the behavior of a minor expressed in the systematic use of alcohol, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances that affect mental activity,

prostitution, begging, as well as other behavior that violates the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of other citizens.

The system of bodies and institutions that carry out the prevention of juvenile delinquency and crime includes:

- interdepartmental commissions on juvenile affairs
- internal affairs bodies;
- educational institutions and authorities;
- health authorities and health care institutions;
- employment and labor relations authorities.

The specified bodies and institutions, within their competence, carry out the prevention of offenses and crime among minors and interact in this direction. In order to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 29, 2019, No. 4342⁵ "On improvement of the activities of specialized educational institutions", minors who have reached 14 years of age and under 18 years of age will be placed in educational institutions of the republic.

The following will be located in the Republic's educational institutions:

who has committed socially dangerous acts, but is not capable of fully understanding the significance of the act committed due to developmental delays for his age, not related to mental illness, or has not reached the age of criminal responsibility;

if the question of guilt has not been resolved and the materials have been transferred for consideration to the interdepartmental commission on juvenile affairs;

minors released from criminal punishment with the use of a compulsory measure in the form of placement in republican educational institutions;

minors who continue to systematically commit offenses or other antisocial behavior, despite the implementation of individual preventive work, are placed on the basis of a court decision.

The status and main tasks of the center are determined on the basis of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 3, 2021, No. 490 "On measures to further improve the provision of social and legal assistance to minors"⁶.

The main areas of work of the Center for Social and Legal Assistance were defined as:

- identify children left without parental care, conduct a thorough study of their upbringing and behavior, family environment, as well as the factors that led to their neglect;

- based on the results of the assessment of the social and legal status of neglected children and a medical examination, transfer them to their parents (persons replacing them) or organize their placement in appropriate institutions (specialized educational, specialized educational and upbringing, children's or medical and preventive institutions);

- provide social and legal assistance to children left without parental care, including providing them with food, basic necessities, clothing, material benefits, organizing temporary shelter and vocational training.

The growth of juvenile crime is one of the problems that seriously worries the world community. The relevance of the topic is characterized by the fact that the direction of the next stage of development of countries is in the hands of the younger generation.

That is, as our president said, "The future and well-being of our planet depend on what kind of people our children grow up to be".

Juveniles commit 30-40 percent of all crimes worldwide, including 40 percent in the UK, 32 percent in the US and 38 percent in Germany.

In conclusion, it is proposed to reorganize the centers for providing social and legal assistance to minors into the "Cluster of Social and Legal Assistance to Children "School of Life"" with the aim of transforming them into a place providing comprehensive social services for working with the problems of children with difficult upbringing and their adaptation to public life